

D7: Report on advanced FRP strengthening system for bridges based on interface efficiency and nanoparticles.

BriFace

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D7: Report on advanced FRP strengthening system for bridges based on interface efficiency and nanoparticles.

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1. Description of toughened adhesive layers.

2. Description of FRP systems.

3. Results -tests/ FEM/bar charts.

4. Conclusions

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D7: Report on advanced FRP strengthening system for bridges based on interface efficiency and nanoparticles.

Matrices for Fiber Reinforced Polymers (FRP).

During the last four decades, the development of advanced composites materials from the theoretical and technological point of view have resulted in an expanded use. Their outstanding engineering properties such as e.g. high tensile strength and stiffness, low density, high fatigue endurance, high damping and low thermal coefficient (in fiber direction), have resulted in a constant use in the aerospace, marine and automobile industries. The FRPs have also been used in structures, new and existing. They function as passive retrofitting measures enhancing strength and ductility [1], [2].

One of the most important matters in FRP applications is, among others, the matrix technology and type. The role of the matrix is to bind together the fibers' reinforcement in order to define the shape and to determine the surface quality. Matrix has to be thermally and chemically compatible with fibers and as such several polymer matrices are used. However, two main types of polymeric matrices are thermosetting and thermoplastic. With a further elaboration thermosetting resins, which are commonly used for FRP composites, result in three types namely polyester resin, vinylester resin, and epoxy resin. These materials offer chemical resistance and thermal stability. Vinylesters, for instance, are resistant to alkalis and strong chemicals [3] and compared with polyesters, they are more effective against moisture absorption and shrinkage, making them suitable for use to manufacture FRP reinforcement bars. Depending on the industry the FRPs are used and the targeted performance and exposure of the application, there are many types of polymers used, such as thermosets (epoxies, phenolics) and thermoplastics (Low Density Polyethylene- LDPE, High Density Polyethylene- HDPE), polypropylene, nylon, acrylics) [3].

The FRP systems consist of the FRP type and an adhesion layer of polymeric base. The polymer most widely used in structural applications is epoxy [5]. These applications have high demands in durability, against exposure in moisture or in extreme corrosive conditions, ice or thermal conditions and exposure to UV radiation [6]. This exposure of the application affects negatively the bond and shear strength up to 30% and therefore the stiffness of the system, resulting to premature failures of adhesion-cohesion type [7]. The premature failures depend on the substrate condition, the type of measure applied, the adhesion layer chosen and the crack propagation at the structural element. The development of premature failures reduces the efficiency of the retrofitting measure.

Especially for bridge retrofitting measures, there is an augmented need for durability in whether conditions e.g. humidity, moisture, ice, thermal expansions, limited cracking in service stress limits and minimum failure of the substrate to ensure no failure occurs and there is continuous. Needless to say, these structures need to exhibit high performance and therefore flexural and shear strength, as well as resistance to fatigue loads. This is due to the importance of such assets to economic and social activities as well as the tremendous impact failures could have not only to economic but mainly to human losses. The novel concept of curing epoxies is to incorporate nanoparticles, such as rubber like particles [8] into the epoxy matrix the overall effectiveness of the strengthening scheme. The nanoparticles alter the properties of the epoxy in order to enhance the shear performance. They permit dislocations and crack propagation at the matrix mass, making it absorb more energy before failure.

1. Description of toughened adhesive layers.

In retrofitting applications of structural elements, 2C epoxies are commonly used as adhesive layers of the FRP system. Two-component (2C) epoxy adhesives allow high-strength bonding of lightweight structures by chemical curing at both "cold" (room temperature) and "hot" (> 80 °C) conditions. These adhesives normally show an elevated tensile modulus and withstand the high level of loads especially static. Due to the brittle nature of their matrix, however, standard epoxy adhesives are characterized by a limited resistance to impact and dynamic loads, which are common in machineries and vehicles across different industries (rail, marine, automotive, commercial transportation, agriculture, wind energy, etc.). For this reason, industrial research has investigated toughening methods for epoxy matrices during the past years [9], introducing a number of 1C and 2C epoxy adhesives with improved impact resistance [10].

D7: Report on advanced FRP strengthening system for bridges based on interface efficiency and nanoparticles.

Using toughening agent in an epoxy adhesive leads to an introduction of small and flexible domains in the epoxy matrix. The smaller and the better dispersed the toughener particles are, the higher the toughness is. In this way, the crash resistance as well as the fatigue performance of epoxy adhesives is enhanced. One chemical approach to form well distributed small particles into a cured epoxy matrix is using reactive toughening polymers. These have to be well dissolved in the resin part and only phase separate upon curing. Such phase-separated toughening particles are shown in Figure 1a&b [10]. Toughening normally results in a matrix with lower stiffness, as the content of dissolved toughener in the matrix increases. Partially, this is intended because material with lower stiffness usually has a higher toughness. The smaller and the better dispersed the toughener particles are, the higher the toughness is. One chemical approach to form well distributed small particles into a cured epoxy matrix is using reactive toughening polymers. The toughened adhesives are expected to absorb more energy before debonding, especially under dynamic load [11] and during the crack propagation when the FRP system is activated and force/stresses are transferred. The toughening for those products is done by incorporation of Polyurethane (PU) rubber like particles into the two component (2C) epoxies. The curing aims at high amounts of elastic domains respecting particles, as small as possible in size and well connected as well as well distributed in the primarily stiff epoxy matrix. However, this process gives the matrix high flexibility, as the content of dissolved toughener in the mix increases. The targeted performance of structural members especially in infrastructure assets, requires a certain stiffness, thus a significant decrease of strength is not desired. As such, an optimal combination of high mechanical performance and increased toughness is the strengthening concept introduced to retrofitting schemes by the industrial partner SIKA AG, as shown in Figure 2 with SmartCore concept.

Especially in refurbishment, a lot of 2C Epoxy adhesives are used for different applications. Even though, considering their highly brittle nature, they are much tougher than concrete and other cementitious or inorganic systems and therefore offer good and reliable bonding. They practically permit the substrate's failure to occur at very elevated levels of loads. For the structural applications and especially for bridge retrofitting schemes, there are augmented requirements for resistance, dynamic loads, stresses and deflections, fatigue cycles and durability. Also, long-prospected lifetime are omnipresent in construction and refurbishment. This advantage of toughened adhesives, combined properly with the substrate and FRP type, open up a new field for structural bonding in construction, e.g. among others seismic reinforcement or construction with novel materials (composite bridges etc.). Due to the increasing age of infrastructure e.g. bridges, together with increasing traffic flow and load and fatigue cycles during its life-time, more and more bridges are in a critical or insufficient condition and require immediate mitigating measures in terms of refurbishment or further adaptability and extension of their life in an ever changing environment. For that reason, Sika transferred its SmartCore toughening technology to the special needs of the strengthening market introducing a novel epoxy layer (Sikadur[®]-370).

The combination of very high mechanical properties, and resistance together with very high fracture toughness are inevitable for strengthening applications. As such, the most important USPs from applications in wind energy and automotive market were combined in one adhesive in order to suit the special needs of structural retrofitting, with a focus initially on metal structures. This resulted in an adhesive with high strength and very high modulus, combined with a high fracture toughness and fatigue resistance with an ultimate goal to increase the lifespan of bonded areas.

The performance of this toughened adhesive was deeply investigated within the German university project FASS (DVS Nr. P09.072 / IGF-Nr. 19032 BG) together with the German universities Cottbus, KIT Karlsruhe and RWTH Aachen. Briface project tests for the first time the suitability of those adhesives in concrete strengthening schemes. Since the Briface project focuses mainly on reinforced concrete and prestressed bridge decks and its elements, the concrete substrate has been simplified as one layer of concrete with a special mix corresponding to bridge deck with very small porous. The novel FRP systems examined based on the enhanced interface performance due to nanoparticles. For these reasons, an experimental campaign and numerical investigation was carried out. The FRP systems' performance has been characterized, focusing at the interface level and on shear stress and slip. The next section describes the new systems and their use in concrete retrofitting schemes.

D7: Report on advanced FRP strengthening system for bridges based on interface efficiency and nanoparticles.

Figure 1. REM images of fracture surfaces of: a) an untoughened epoxy matrix and b) a toughened epoxy matrix with well-distributed approximately 1 µm rubber-like particles formed upon curing.

Figure 2. Smartcore Technology concept for adhesive layers' stiffness- SIKA AG.

2. Description of FRP systems.

The FRP strengthening systems consists of two parts: a) the toughened adhesive layer Sikadur- 370 and b) the combination with FRP of different form. The following tables show those systems (Table 1) combined in order to examine the behavior of the interface if adhesion is enhanced with nanoparticles. One type of FRPs were chosen with carbon fibers (CFRP) since it is the commonly used type for bridge retrofitting schemes due to the mechanical properties The systems were also compared to bonded FRP

D7: Report on advanced FRP strengthening system for bridges based on interface efficiency and nanoparticles.

with standard epoxy. Table 2 contains the mechanical properties of the three adhesives examined. The adhesives and FRP types were combined based on the compatibility between the materials (Table 3).

Table 1: Mechanical properties of CFRPs.

type	density ρ [kg/L]	tensile strength σ_u [MPa]	E-modulus	
			(0.05-0.25%) [GPa]	tensile strain ϵ (EAB) [%]
Prefabricated plates- Carbodur S	1.6	3100	170	1.8
Fabrics- SikaWrap	1.8	4900	230	1.7

Table 2: Mechanical properties of epoxy adhesives.

type	density ρ [kg/L]	tensile strength σ_u [MPa]	E-modulus (0.05-0.25%) [GPa]	tensile strain ϵ (EAB) [%]
Sikadur®-30	~ 2	26	9500	0.3
Sikadur®-330	~1.4	29	4000	1
Sikadur®-370	~1.7	30	5000	2.5

Table 3. FRP strengthening systems.

FRP type	Adhesive system	Numbers of specimens (test)	Substrate conditions	
			healthy	corroded
prefabricated plates	Sikadur-30	3	X	X
	Sikadur-370	3	X	X
Laminated fabrics	Sikadur-330	3	X	X
	Sikadur-370	3	X	X
Near Surface Mounted (NSM)	Sikadur-30	3	X	X
	Sikadur-330	3	X	X
	Sikadur-370	3	X	X

The interaction with the concrete substrate to the dislocations imposed is usually examined with double-lap shear tests with the FRPs applied to concrete prisms externally bonded. The bond behavior between the concrete surface and the composites have been investigated widely with single or double lap shear tests of various setups. These configurations permit the direct examination of the shear stresses of the interface. The differences of the methods rely on the premature failures that may occur or even relative slip [12], [13], [14], [15], [16], **Error! Reference source not found.** A modification of the classic double-lap shear setup was made and a direct measurement of the shear resistance and slip was measured [17], [18], [19]. Since the novel systems are aimed to provide novel solutions for bridge retrofitting schemes, the investigation includes different conditions of the concrete substrate. That is healthy concrete or containing corroded steel rebars, one of the major reasons why bridges nowadays

D7: Report on advanced FRP strengthening system for bridges based on interface efficiency and nanoparticles.

are decaying. The tremendous impact of the corrosion of steel reinforcement in strength loss and ductility influences also the mitigation measures of retrofitting. The corrosion products leaching to the concrete external faces and sides shift the bind behavior and finally the interface response of existing concrete and integrated composite material.

3.1 Double-lap shear test description

This study adopts a modified double lap shear test (Figure 3). This involves instead of the classic two concrete blocks, only one concrete block where the FRPs are applied and are gripped to the protruding end. The concrete block lays on a hollow support which permits slip and is hanged from the gripped ends of the FRPs that are fixed to a rigid steel frame (Figure 3a). This alteration of the setup limits the relative slips of the interfaces of the two different blocks, eliminates slips at the gripped ends of the FRP and at the same time permits direct shear stress measurement (Figure 3b). The tests were performed on a compression machine at a speed of 1mm/min at a room temperature (20°C). the measurements of the deformation of the central part of the CFRP at the central path (Figure 1a) were recorded using a high accuracy laser sensor. Also, two Linear Displacement Transducers (LDVT) with a maximum capacity of 100mm, were used to measure the displacement of the upper level of the concrete block and the grips.

Figure 3. Double lap shear setup , a) schematic representation, b) assembled in the lab.

3.2 Preparation of specimens.

3.2.1 Materials.

Forty-two concrete blocks are designed in this study with dimensions 150x150x250mm and were prepared according to [20], [21], [22], [23] and were casted in situ in collaboration with the Reinforced concrete and Seismic Design Laboratory of Democritus University of Thrace in Xanthi, Greece (Figure 4). The concrete mix had a 28-day compressive strength of 37.5 MPa corresponding to a tensile strength of 3MPa (Table 4). All blocks contained a steel rebar (500MPa) of 18mm diameter in the middle of the cross section placed longitudinally to the concrete block. Three different commercialized CFRP strengthening schemes were chosen (laminated fabrics, prefabricated plates and Near Surface Mounted-NSM, see Table 3). All CFRPs were bonded symmetrically on opposite sides of the concrete blocks at a bond length of 200mm with dry lay-up process, using different bi-component epoxies curing at ambient environment (Table 2). The CFRP strengthening materials were initially investigated both with

D7: Report on advanced FRP strengthening system for bridges based on interface efficiency and nanoparticles.

a standard epoxy, Sikadur®-30 for the prefabricated plates and Sikadur®-330 laminated sheets. Additionally, both strengthening schemes, were repeated using a newly available toughened epoxy adhesive (Sikadur®-370) designed for fatigue resistance long lasting reinforcement of steel bridges [24]. The NSM strengthening schemes were designed, though not included in this research. The laminated fabrics and prefabricates plates retrofitting measures are of high importance for the interface response, especially since they exhibit specific failures, and they have a considerable larger interface area in respect to the NSM measures. Therefore, the study of the force transfer and the propagation of failure on the interface of these CFRP measures is prioritized.

Table 4: Composition of the concrete mixture.

material	cement CEM I	natural sand	crushed sand	aggregate coarse		water
				medium	large	
quantity (kgr/m ³)	310	621	351	236	638	191

a)

b)

Figure 4. Preparation of specimens in the lab: a) moulds, b) concreting.

3.2.2 Accelerated corrosion.

The corrosion conditions are usually simulated in the lab using NaCl solution and a current flow in a tank (Figure 5). Nine concrete prisms were exposed to wet conditions in a special tank. They were bathed in a 3.5-5% weight NaCl-water solution (Figure 5a), which covered one third of the cross-section size of the concrete blocks [25][26][27]. A low ratio of corrosion of the steel rebar cross-section is created almost equal to 6% with a continuous power supply ($\approx 1\text{mA}$) [28] wired in the steel rebars for about three weeks (Figure 5b, c). The crack opening of the concrete blocks ($w=0.1\text{-}0.35\text{mm}$) and the loss of rebar cross section (\sim loss of diameter equal to 0.4mm) simulates exceeding service limit states conditions but not severe deterioration in ultimate limit states (Figure 6). The samples were also

D7: Report on advanced FRP strengthening system for bridges based on interface efficiency and nanoparticles.

exposed, except for the wet conditions, in dry conditions on-site, before the application of the FRPs [29]. After this period, the tensile strength of concrete was assessed with other experiments from the international literature to avoid patch repair in the case of experimental measurement with pull-off tests [30], [31], [32].

Figure 5. Accelerated corrosion: a) tank with salt mixture, b) current flow wiring, c) leaching corrosion products.

D7: Report on advanced FRP strengthening system for bridges based on interface efficiency and nanoparticles.

a)

b)

c)

Figure 6. Crack pattern: a) cracks developing in parallel to the steel rebar, b) leaching corrosion with T shape crack in the cross-section, c) crack width range (0.1-0.35mm).

3.2.3 FRP application.

The composite strengthening systems were bonded symmetrically on opposite sides of the blocks with a bonding length of 200mm on each side. The fibre orientation in case of fabrics was 0° along the longitudinal direction of concrete blocks. The prefabricated plates were cleaned with the special

D7: Report on advanced FRP strengthening system for bridges based on interface efficiency and nanoparticles.

solvent-based cleaner Sika® Colma Cleaner, to remove oil, grease and dust, at least 15 minutes before the application. The systems were applied with a dry lay-up process and according to the technical specification of the manufacturer. The interfaces were treated properly to have a laitance contaminant free, open textured surface (Figure 5a-i,ii) and were cleaned with air pressure to remove loose material, dust and rust (Figure 5a-iii). The two components' epoxy adhesives (Table 3) were mixed according to the manufacturer's recommended weight ratio and time (3:1 for Sikadur®-30, 4:1 for Sikadur®-330 and 100:74 for Sikadur®-370). The composites are left to cure at ambient conditions (20°C, 50% relative humidity-RH) for at least a week before testing (Figure 5a-v, b).

Figure 5. Preparation of specimens with dry-up application: a) interface treatment, b) curing at ambient environment.

3. Results.

The experimental data of all tested specimens is summarised in Table 5. The same table also includes the data of the average curve which represents the tendency of the three specimens of each group of samples during the shear test. The numerical results are illustrated as a distribution graph along the length of the interface (see Section 4.2.2). Also, the FEM analysis permitted the investigation at each layer and the sliding representation of the interface.

3.1 Experimental results

4.1.1 Failure modes

The response as well as the failure mode of each group of specimens is mainly cohesive- adhesive and are shown in Figure 6. For the groups with laminated fabrics, that is sh330x3HI and sh370x3HI and

D7: Report on advanced FRP strengthening system for bridges based on interface efficiency and nanoparticles.

sh330x3Cr, the failure mechanism was progressive and result from the development of cracks on the concrete mass, followed by detachment of the applied composite sheet after it was tensed [33], regardless of the existence of corrosion products. Due to the consistency of the laminated sheets (carbon), the elongation is not measurable and as such it is not considered in the following analysis. FRP rupture is met in only one case, where the epoxy's ultimate strain is considerably larger than that of the FRP (Figure 7) but generally the dominant failure is mainly adhesive-cohesive. This case only accounted when a toughened adhesive was used to bond the laminated sheets. Based on that fact, as well as on the adhesion failure mode depicted in Figure 6, a clear impact of the toughness of the adhesive is recognized. Due to the induced toughness, the stress on the bonded material is divided on larger surfaces. The rubber particles cavitate and trigger shear deformation in the matrix or the epoxy [34], [35], [36], resulting in substrate failure as shown in Figure 6 g & h. For the case of laminated fabrics, the use of the toughened epoxy resulted in failure mode, that is FRP rupture for both substrates (Figure 6c&d). Whereas, the use of usual high mechanical brittle adhesive layers, leads to a more adhesive failure, induced to high peak stresses at the borders of the composites (see Figure 6 a,b & e, f). This progressive failure mode is also noted at the response curve. The substrate crack propagation to the adhesive layer is indicated by the transition points [37] after which detachment occurs gradually (Figure 7). The transition points practically correspond to the strengthening system's, that is the combination of the adhesive layer and FRP, propagating failure and progressive delamination up to debonding. The failure mode of the prefabricated plates, that is pl30x3Hl, pl30x3Cr, pl370x3Hl and pl370x3Cr, was also of adhesion-cohesion type. All the specimens exhibited brittle failure with the plate being debonded from the concrete. (Figures 6 e-h). The results are presented in shear stress- shear deformation diagrams of the average curves for the different categories of specimens (Figure 7).

4.1.2 FRP laminated fabrics.

Specimens with laminated sheets (sh330x3Hl, sh330x3Cr) of unidirectional carbon fibers bonded with the epoxy adhesive layer Sikadur®-330, present a response in three distinct stages, shown in Figure 7. The adhesive layer limits the substrate's failure propagation, allow the fracture to happen in stages and absorb more energy before debonding. The low elasticity of the matrix (epoxy layer) in combination with the increased strain limit, permit the epoxy to absorb more energy before failure.

In the first stage the fabric is under tension (Stage I: linear elastic) in a linear rate. The direction of the laminated sheets' fibers that are in parallel to the loading direction prevents bridging the crack propagation. In the second stage, there is a progressive crack initiation of the epoxy layer leading to crack opening, followed by a non-linear elastic yielding branch up to the transition point (Stage II: non-linear elastic yielding). The transition point (τ^{trans} , γ^{trans}) practically corresponds to the further propagation of the crack pattern at the resin and the substrate and the overall connection of the two materials. The third stage is characterized by major cracking both at the adhesive layer and the substrate. Plastic regions are created at the concrete, and especially at the initial debonding area at a distance approximately equal to 5 cm from the loading end. At the ultimate point of this stage (Stage III: major cracking), the specimens exhibit debonding of the FRP (τ^u , γ^u). The failure mode is mainly caused due to adhesion loss at the delamination area and no FRP rupture is met (Figure 8a).

The effect of the corroded steel rebars on the interface response of this group is also shown in Figure 8. The green dashed line represents the average curve of specimens with corroded steel rebar with laminated sheets applied on the concrete substrate with epoxy adhesive layer Sikadur®-330, whereas the red solid line represents the average curve of the healthy specimens containing the same epoxy. There is a clear difference in the response in both cases. The interface of the substrate with corrosion products (330_corroded_ave) presents a 20% decrease in shear strength (τ^u) and 24% lower shear deformation (γ^u) at the ultimate point (Table 5).

D7: Report on advanced FRP strengthening system for bridges based on interface efficiency and nanoparticles.

a)

b)

c)

d)

D7: Report on advanced FRP strengthening system for bridges based on interface efficiency and nanoparticles.

e)

f)

g)

h)

Figure 6. Failure modes of CFRP adhesively bonded in healthy or corroded substrate with compatible a), b), e) & f) or toughened matrix c), d), g) & h).

D7: Report on advanced FRP strengthening system for bridges based on interface efficiency and nanoparticles.

Also, the transition point is shifted to lower values of deformations (52%) and strength (18%). The leached corrosion products laying on the sides of the concrete prisms and the minor strains due to the initiation of corrosion are considered practically as mass disturbance and create regions of altered consistency and resistance. Even in such early stages of corrosion, which corresponds to corrosion initiation and to allowable bond values of the substrate for immediate interventions, the cracks in the concrete mass in combination with the rust laying on the interface, makes the connection with the FRP strengthening scheme weaker and results in lower values of slip and shear strength.

Sikadur® 370 is a new developed toughened epoxy adhesive combining high toughness with higher stiffness and strength, also showing a high fatigue strength [11], [38]. This makes it ideal for strengthening steel substrates in retrofitting applications [39]. Its good adhesion and good anti-corrosion performance make it an optimal solution to be applied in extreme corroded environments even onto concrete substrates [17]. A matrix having 25% higher stiffness presents a different response (sh370x3Hl, Table 4). This group of specimens having laminated sheets bonded with epoxy adhesive layer 370 (Sikadur®-370) resented a rather brittle behavior. This is illustrated in Figure 8a&b, where it is noted that the tougher the matrix is, the stages II and III coincide. Its intrinsic toughness is proven to enhance the capacity of the substrate to bear the shear stresses, though it presents a rather elastic response. The transition point in this case is remarkably clear and decreased per 80% in respect to the corresponding case of Sikadur®-330 layer. This means that the failure propagation of the substrate starts at different stress rates. Even though there is a distinct transition point in almost the same levels of shear deformations yet in higher values of shear stresses (70% higher at transition point and 2.5 times higher at ultimate), the crack pattern both in the substrate and in the adhesive layer propagates simultaneously up to the debonding point of the strengthening system. This intrinsic toughened adhesive layer Sikadur®-370 is designed for steel substrates and especially suitable for fatigue cracking applications. The crack width in the cases of concrete substrates is larger than fatigue cracking in steel substrates. In combination with the stiffness of the matrix, the response alters from pseudo-plastic (case of Sikadur®-330) to brittle and the failure mode from adhesive-cohesive to FRP rupture (Figure 6c).

For this strengthening scenario using the toughened matrix the effect of corrosion and rust is also examined illustrated also in Figure 3b with the blue dashed line. In that case the response is similar to the healthy substrate case, however a decrease in the values of shear stress and strains is noted. The difference of the corresponding healthy case is almost 43% in ultimate shear stress and 62% in shear strains at the ultimate point. Also, the stages are compressed and the transition point is presented earlier in almost half the strains and stresses of the healthy substrate.

In terms of the absorbed energy, specimens with toughened epoxies exhibit on average 15% higher energy, when the substrate is healthy (Figure 9a). In the case that rust has leached on the surfaces and corrosion process has initiated, then the response differs significantly. For the case of the standard epoxy, the absorption of energy decreases on average 40%, whereas, the toughened epoxies on corroded substrates the energy absorbed in almost one third of the corresponding standard epoxy (Figure 9b).

4.1.3 FRP prefabricated plates

For the case of specimens with prefabricated plates bonded with different adhesive layers there is a significant increase at the initial stiffness equal to 10%. The shear deformations range in comparatively lower (50-85%) values in respect to the group bonded with laminated sheets. The failure mode is similar for all groups. The delamination is abrupt at the ultimate point and ends in a brittle debonding mechanism. The fundamental difference of the prefabricated plates to the laminated sheets is the much higher stiffness and mechanical properties. The strengthening in that case is much stronger and the response of the CRP type is dominant and governs the failure mode. The contribution of the different adhesives is minor mainly noticeable to weaker strengthening schemes, such as laminated sheets.

D7: Report on advanced FRP strengthening system for bridges based on interface efficiency and nanoparticles.

Specimens with plates bonded externally with the standard adhesive Sikadur®-30 present a bilinear response. In Figure 8c the two distinct stages are exhibited. There is a clear transition point between the two stages, yet the second branch is quite abrupt. Analogously to the wrapped specimens, the transition point denotes the propagating delamination and crack opening.

The group with Sikadur®-370 epoxy adhesive layer (Figure 8b, yellow dotted line pl_370_H1) present a shifted behavior in cases of the prefabricated plates, especially if compared to the results of Sikadur®-30 adhesive layer. As noted in specimens with laminated sheets, also in the case of plates, the stages are compressed and the response is mainly linear. Failure happens in lower stress values (12%) and in remarkably lower values of shear deformations, reaching up to 24% decrease. The CFRP prefabricated plates strengthening measure has no capacity to bridge the crack opening of both the epoxy and the substrate and therefore the debonding is ‘premature’.

Regarding the effect of the integrity of the substrate to the bond slip behavior of the strengthening scheme, there is a strong impact due to the existence of the corrosion products at the connected interfaces. Both in terms of strains and stresses, there is a remarkable decrease of shear deformation up to 47% for the ultimate point. In all cases, the stages are compacted and the stress rates are similar. In this group, the early corrosion level effect is minor in both cases of adhesive layers. For the case of Sikadur®-30 epoxy, debonding happens in 10% lower values of shear strains as summarised also in Table 5. Whereas, for the toughened layer the response is similar.

In terms of the absorbed energy, the scheme differs in respect to the laminated fabrics. The specimens with toughened epoxies exhibit on average 84% lower energy, when the substrate is healthy (Figure 9c). In the case that rust has leached on the surfaces and corrosion process has initiated, then the response differs significantly. For the case of the standard epoxy, the absorption of energy decreases on average 85%, whereas, the toughened epoxies on corroded substrates the energy absorbed in almost 45% higher than that of the corresponding standard epoxy (Figure 9d).

Figure 7. Failure propagation in distinct stages.

D7: Report on advanced FRP strengthening system for bridges based on interface efficiency and nanoparticles.

Figure 8. Shear stress vs shear strain results of double lap tests for healthy and corroded substrate: a) & b) for laminated fabrics and c) & d) for prefabricated plates.

D7: Report on advanced FRP strengthening system for bridges based on interface efficiency and nanoparticles.

Figure 9. Absorbed energy E (MJ/m³) of double lap shear tests for healthy and corroded substrate using different epoxy matrices: a) & b) for laminated CFRP fabrics and c) & d) for prefabricated plates.

Table 5: Experimental results of double-lap shear tests.

	healthy substrate					with corroded products						
	τ^{trans} (MPa)	τ^u (MPa)	γ^{trans} (%)	γ^u (%)	E (MJ/m ³)	τ^{trans} (MPa)	τ^u (MPa)	γ^{trans} (%)	γ^u (%)	E (MJ/m ³)		
Laminated sheets	HI330_1	1.25	1.48	0.72	1.33	1.56	Cr330_1	0.94	1.11	0.47	1.73	1.59
	HI330_2	1.28	1.38	0.57	1.46	1.76	Cr330_2	0.99	1.20	0.32	0.60	0.51
	HI330_3	0.82	1.37	0.6	0.91	0.84	Cr330_3	0.83	1.09	0.12	0.47	0.39
	average 330	1.12	1.41	0.63	1.23	1.39	average 330	0.92	1.13	0.30	0.93	0.83
	HI370_1	1.97	3.58	0.2	0.67	1.70	Cr370_1	0.95	1.80	0.09	0.22	0.26
	HI370_2	1.80	3.57	0.12	0.63	1.59	Cr370_2	1.30	2.20	0.14	0.25	0.37
	HI370_3	1.94	3.56	0.07	0.65	1.73	Cr370_3	1.20	2.10	0.18	0.28	0.38
	average 370	1.90	3.57	0.17	0.65	1.63	average 370	1.15	2.03	0.14	0.25	0.34
abs error 370-330	41%	61%	263%	90%	15%	abs error 370-330	20%	44%	122%	273%	147%	
Prefabricated plates	HI30_1	1.50	2.55	0.11	0.73	1.42	Cr30_1	-	3.00	-	0.13	0.20
	HI30_2	1.92	2.38	0.11	0.14	0.28	Cr30_2	-	2.50	-	0.19	0.24
	HI30_3	1.80	3.52	0.11	0.60	1.50	Cr30_3	-	2.10	-	0.05	0.05
	average 30	1.74	2.82	0.11	0.49	1.06	average 30	-	2.53	-	0.12	0.15
	HI370_1	-	3.50	-	0.09	0.16	Cr370_1	-	3.05	-	0.12	0.18
	HI370_2	-	3.17	-	0.11	0.17	Cr370_2	-	2.90	-	0.21	0.30
	HI370_3	-	2.80	-	0.12	0.17	Cr370_3	-	3.35	-	0.14	0.24
	average 370	-	3.16	-	0.11	0.17	average 370	-	3.10	-	0.16	0.25
abs error 370-30	-	10%	-	75%	84%	abs error 370-30	-	2%	-	47%	40%	

4.2 Finite element modelling.

For a more thorough and close micro-analysis of the failure modes and interface investigation, a Finite Element Analysis (FEA) was conducted using the commercial software ANSYS. The Cohesive Zone Models (CZM) have been extensively used to simulate the fracture of ductile and brittle solids [40], the delamination of composites from substrates [41] and the behaviour of adhesively bonded composites [42], [43], [44], [45]. These models consist of a constitutive relation between stresses of the interface and the corresponding interfacial relative displacements (slip) of the connected materials. They simulate the elastic response up to the peak load, initiation of damage and further propagation due to local failure of a material/contact, sometimes followed by a softening response, to model the gradual degradation of material properties up to complete failure. The areas of the CZM correspond to the fracture energy needed for failure. Mode II debonding represents a mode of separation of the interface where tangential slip dominates the separation normal to the interface.

4.2.1 Interface investigation.

The debonding of FRP composites applied to the concrete substrate was simulated with a bilinear CZM fracture model (Figure 10) which was calibrated from the experimental results. Concrete and CFRPs were treated as homogeneous isotropic linear-elastic materials and were connected through zero thickness interfaces. Concrete and composites were simulated using a 3-d solid element, defined by eight nodes having three degrees of freedom at each node: translations in the nodal x, y, and z directions.

Model calibration is a cornerstone for the FE model in order to have credibility. This is achieved by comparing with the test data. The calibration, in which a minimum deviation within acceptable limits is met, between the FEM results and the corresponding test data, is an optimization process with many parameters to consider, with deviation metrics that are usually nonlinear [39][46], [47]. The calibration was achieved in two stages: first the mechanical parameters of the adhesive (linear) were defined and second, the failure mode (nonlinear) mechanism.

Figure 10. Bilinear CZM model for interface simulation.

4.2.2 Stress and strain distribution

The finite element simulations' results calculated based on the response that each group exhibited during the tests. Simulation was performed for healthy concrete substrates with both CFRP types, laminated fabrics and prefabricated plates, bonded each group with the two different adhesives studied experimentally. Figure 11 illustrates a representation of the cross-section of the tested prisms with externally bonded CFRPs in the two opposite sides. The simulation helped to define the stress-strain field through the distribution diagrams **Error! Reference source not found.**[48], [49] shown in Figure 12 and 13. The stress and strain field assists also in defining the effective length and width of the

D7: Report on advanced FRP strengthening system for bridges based on interface efficiency and nanoparticles.

interface (Figure 11b), as well as the plastification area of concrete. Figure 11c illustrates the location of the two paths A and B for which numerical results are reported in Figures 12 and 13. Path A corresponds to the outer limit of the connection of concrete and FRP, whereas path B is located at the central axis of the CFRP and the concrete prism, both in the side of the interface.

Figure 11. Concrete prisms: a) cross-section with CFRPs configuration, b) stress distribution along the interface, c) interface's paths' location.

The field distribution along the path presented a concentration of stresses near the loading end ($L_y=240\text{mm}$), presenting matching of the failure modes noted at the end of each test. Stresses and strains are normalised for each group based on the maximum values noted at the end of the test, which were also validated with the numerical simulations. As such, the vertical axes are in the form of percentages of the limit values achieved. The Figures 12 and 13 include also a cumulative curve, noted with green colour which shows the total stress of both FRP composites bonded, the concrete prism and the interface contribution to the allocation, which are also reported separately. The differences in the distribution graphs for the two different paths denote that there is a slightly higher ($\pm 10\%$) concentration of stresses near the outer limit of the connection (path A). This uniformity of the stresses along the width advocates for the cohesive-adhesive failure type. For the case of laminated fabrics, both for adhesive Sikadur®-330 and 370 (Figures 12a&b), the stress concentration is increased closed to the loading end ($L_y=240\text{mm}$) and fades significantly after the 50% of the length. The failure propagation differs and it is reported in Figures 12c&d. For the case of Sikadur®-370, the sliding distance graph denotes that the failure is brittle. The significant sliding ($>40\%$) is not extended over the whole length of the interface, it is limited in a distance of 80mm close to the loading end, which is 33% limited in respect to Sikadur®-330 case. The interface contribution is also considerably lower and the inclination is quite steep. This lack of distribution of strains along the length results to a more brittle failure, the epoxy absorbs more energy and strains and limits the propagation of cracks at the substrate.

The distribution for the prefabricated plates is analogous, though presents differences (Figure 13). The first significant difference is the steeper inclination of all the curves. The stresses fade in a length 25% closer to the loading end in respect to the laminated sheets (Figure 13 a&b). The brittle performance is more evident since there is no broad strain distribution and the sliding is not propagating but is concentrated to the loading area, that is $L_y=200\text{mm}$ and onwards (Figure 13c&d) and the toughened adhesive absorbs more energy.

D7: Report on advanced FRP strengthening system for bridges based on interface efficiency and nanoparticles.

The stress-strain field's shape validate and correspond to the distinct stages of cracking, distinguished with the clear transition point in test results and further confirm the failure mechanism and propagation. In cases the distribution is steep, short and limited close to the loading end, the failure is brittle. The more the inclination presents shifts, the more plastic the response tends to be.

Figure 12. Stress (a&b)-strain (sliding-c&d) distribution for the case of laminated fabrics bonded to healthy concrete substrate for different adhesive layers.

D7: Report on advanced FRP strengthening system for bridges based on interface efficiency and nanoparticles.

Figure 13. Stress (a&b)-strain (sliding-c&d) distribution for the case of prefabricated plates bonded to healthy concrete substrate for different adhesive layers.

Figure 14 shows the contour plots of the FEA illustrating the sliding and the total stresses on the interface area between the concrete substrate and the FRP fabric. The stresses present a similar value for both healthy and corroded substrates. Both cases, have a concentration of stresses near the loading end, presenting similar failure modes. It is also remarkable that the active length of the interface, meaning the length which concentrates the highest ratios of stresses, is 5% lower in the case of the corroded substrate. Also, for the healthy substrate the middle part of the fabric, around path B, concentrates more stresses, denoting the higher ratio of loads transferred to the FRP fabric through the interface layer.

D7: Report on advanced FRP strengthening system for bridges based on interface efficiency and nanoparticles.

Figure 14. Contour plots of the interface for laminated fabrics a) total stresses, b) sliding distance.

healthy substrate

3.2 Interfacial response and efficiency.

According to the equations as proposed and presented in Deliverable 6, the Interface Capacity (IC) indices for all groups of specimens of the experimental campaign are calculated (Table 6) and are illustrated in the bar chart in Figure 15. The group of specimens with the laminated fabrics bonded present higher values of the index, both for healthy and substrates with corrosion products. The IC index is up to 2.45 times higher for the same epoxy adhesive (Sikadur®-370) in respect to the prisms with prefabricated plates. Each group presents indices of the same magnitude and correspond to a different type of performance as well as failure.

The results show that the limit for exhibiting a pseudoplastic response of the interface is IC equal to 2.5, as it is noted with the dashed red line in Figure 15. This is the limit value of the IC index under which the response tends to be premature and brittle with abrupt debonding, meaning a fully elastic interface response.

This limit differentiates the response of the two major groups of specimens of the study, that is the first with externally bonded laminated sheets (grey bars) and the second with the prefabricated plates bonded (green dashed bars). The IC index represents the overall capacity of the interface to bear stresses and strains and is the sum of the two individuals, IC_L and IC_{fp} , as discussed previously. CFRP plates exhibit higher stiffness and mechanical properties as mentioned in previously and therefore have a dominant role. The interface capacity is lower since the adhesive properties are not evident in such strengthening schemes.

The chart also demonstrates the effect of the presence of corrosion products to the substrate. There is a clear reduction of the same magnitude for the different CFRP cases, equal to 20%, regardless the type of the CFRP used.

The efficiency of the FRP measure is quantified by the Interface Capacity index which categorizes the retrofitting schemes into two distinct classes: a) fully brittle ($IC < 2.5$) or b) pseudoplastic ($IC > 2.5$). Fabrics are proven to be more efficient than plates, since the deformability of the system before failure

D7: Report on advanced FRP strengthening system for bridges based on interface efficiency and nanoparticles.

is larger. Finally, the toughened adhesive layer, absorbs energy and get deformations helping the measure to present a non-elastic response.

Figure 15. Interface Capacity (IC) indices bar chart.

Table 6: Interface capacity indexes for double lap specimens.

		healthy			corroded		
		IC _L	IC _{fp}	IC	IC _L	IC _{fp}	IC
Laminated fabrics	Sikadur 330	4.13	0.17	4.30	3	0.17	3.44
	Sikadur 370	3.71	0.18	3.89	3	0.14	3.11
Prefabricated plates	Sikadur 30	1.01	1.51	2.52	1	1.21	2.02
	Sikadur 370	0.94	0.8	1.74	1	0.64	1.39

4. Conclusions

This report describes the investigation of strengthening systems of composite materials for bridges based on interface efficiency and nanoparticles. It includes results of both a numerical and an experimental study, part of a wider and expanded experimental campaign. The cornerstone of this report was to investigate the ratio of enhancement of the interface layers of such strengthening measures using nanoparticles. The FRP systems were enhanced with epoxy adhesives which were enriched with rubber-like nanoparticles (PU) making them tough. Those adhesives have the ability to absorb more energy and are sensitive to dislocations. The main parameters examined are a) the FRP strengthening type, b) the kind of the epoxy adhesive layer and c) the existence of corrosion products laying on the interface, corresponding to early stages of corrosion and limited crack pattern ($w < 0.3\text{mm}$). The force transfer ratio and the failure propagation of the substrates were quantified using the Interface Capacity index proposed in D6 in order to measure the efficiency of the different strengthening systems. To conclude, the following points are extracted:

1. Enhancing CFRP strengthening schemes for concrete substrates with toughened adhesive layers with lower stiffness matrix exhibit more abrupt failures, achieving higher stresses. The tougher the adhesive is the more brittle the behavior becomes. The overall interface capacity is similar in CFRP fabrics but decreased in adhesively bonded

D7: Report on advanced FRP strengthening system for bridges based on interface efficiency and nanoparticles.

plates. The dispersion of stresses when using toughened adhesives should be further investigated in larger areas of substrates.

2. The type of CFRP plays an important role to the response of the interface. The direction of fibers of the composite can bridge the gaps from the crack development. The different composite types in combination with the adhesive layer can permit the strain distribution in a more extended area. Prefabricated plates have much higher stiffness and mechanical properties in respect to laminated sheets and govern the failure mode. The adhesive layer limits the substrate's failure propagation, allow the fracture to happen in stages and absorbs satisfactory energy before debonding. The contribution of the different adhesives is mainly evident in the cases of laminated fabrics.
3. The corrosion of the steel rebars embedded at the concrete substrate has a strong impact on the response of the FRP system. It results in lower levels of stresses and strains, ranging up to 20% for shear stresses and 23% for shear strains at the ultimate point for the standard epoxy and at around 43% and 62% respectively, for the toughened one. Also, the crack propagation is faster. The effective length of the strengthening system should be considered increased in such cases, in order to have the adhesive properties of the matrix fully developed.
4. The failure mode is predominantly cohesive-adhesive. The induced toughened epoxies absorb more energy and distribute stresses/strains in the matrix in contrast to the usual high mechanical brittle adhesive layers that leads to adhesive failure with peak stresses concentrated at the borders of the composites.
5. Strengthening adhesives do not necessarily need high values of mechanical properties. Toughened epoxy adhesives introduce moderately reduced stiffness for bonding FRPs still ensuring high strengthening performance for concrete retrofitting cases. Toughened epoxies exhibit a satisfactory response and can be a strengthening scheme that has a combination of low level of stiffness and high strain capacity. In this way, the absorbed by the epoxy energy is higher, and permits the failure to be dislocated at the FRP system and with no significant failure propagation at the substrate.

Based on the above results and conclusions, more research is needed with intermediate epoxies properties to validate the model (semi-empirical) for the quantification of IC and provide values of indexes with interpolation for any kind of epoxy adhesive layer- composite combination.

D7: Report on advanced FRP strengthening system for bridges based on interface efficiency and nanoparticles.

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